

The Objectivity of Users' Emotional Experience with Textiles

Biological and Mechanical Tests for the Prediction of the Sensorial Profile of Fabrics.

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Abstract: Sensorial and emotional loads, which are strongly correlated to the acceptability of fabrics to users and the pleasure users derive from them, represent a decisive factor in the application of textiles. For the past few years this research group has been investigating modalities to define and predict sensoriality on the basis of objective parameters and tests. In the current phase of research a broader panel of test subjects has been constituted to verify and further investigate previous results. The panel includes professional figures, foreigners, blind people and laypeople. As well as this, the adoption of experimental mechanical tests aimed at replicating users' skin properties and procedures in valuing the hand of fabrics has led to new findings and further improvements. Reliable results have been obtained for the prediction of sensorial properties such as softness, smoothness and lightness on the basis of specific objective tests. The most novel contributions derive from investigations in the field of neurosciences. Panelists were monitored in their physiological parameters (skin-resistance and heart-rate) and sight directions (eye-tracking) while assessing fabrics to identify task difficulty rankings and exploratory paths.

Keywords: *Textiles, electro dermal activity, sensory analysis, hand, eye-tracking.*

1. Introduction and background

The emotional load of industrial products is strongly related to the sensorial information conveyed by materials. Designers have been conscious of this important issue for several decades, as shown by the attempts of one of the most important historical design schools, the Bauhaus, which studied and used materials for their expressive load and sensorial emotional potentials. Consistent attention has also been devoted to textiles [1,2].

Nowadays numerous research fields contribute to the investigation of a potential correlation between the expressive sensorial dimension of materials and their physical mechanical properties [3,4]. Some focus on tactile perception, especially contributing to the goal of predicting consumers' emotional responses to products by characterizing some of the relationships between the dimensions of touch perception and the physical properties of the texture involved [5].

For the last few years our research has focused particularly on the emotional value of textiles [6,7,8].

Fabrics imply an intimate contact with the skin due to their primary use in the clothing industry. Historically, the main application of textiles, i.e. clothing realization, suggests the creation of products which cover, protect and insulate the human body from both atmospheric events and wounds, thus augmenting quality of life and comfort.

A continuous protection from external agents tends to stimulate sensations of physical and psychological wellness, implying that the ideal wellness condition may be reached through the optimization of the properties of fabrics. The studies on thermal comfort, cleaning, resistance and anthropometrical data in clothing design are broad and clear, whilst documents examining the sensory reaction invoked by textiles are more fragmentary and vague. This may be caused by the difficulty in determining pleasure requirements, which must be identified according to the user. Also important is the context of use, trends, and the increasingly reduced thickness of the layer of the fabric itself.

For the past few years our research has been investigating the sensoriality of materials and objective methods to predict the sensorial profile of particular materials such as fabrics [6].

In the latest phase of research we utilized concepts and tools from the neurosciences in order to measure the effects of materials on users and the emotions these materials generated. “Artifacts which constitute the material world have the ability to elicit a variety of effects on users. These effects are variable according to the user, their interpretation and subjectivity.” [9]. In the context of emotions, objective measurement plays an important role. It has been confirmed that stimuli provoke certain effects in a user’s brain, and measurement permits an understanding of the magnitude of these effects. Eye-tracking and skin-resistance measurement tools were used in this step of the research.

2. Studies on hand

Sensoriality of fabrics, usually called “hand” or “handle”, has been a research topic since the beginning of the last century. Among informal approaches to the sensoriality of textiles, Annie Albers carried out some brilliant research on expressivity of fabrics during textiles and design courses at Bauhaus.

The hand of textiles can be studied and described from several points of view and thus pursued in multiple directions according to specific purposes and fields, from a psycho-physics theory to an information theory [10].

In our laboratories we are investigating the correlation of the sensations provoked by textiles and their corresponding emotional profiles to physical mechanical properties strictly correlated to the Fabric Objective Measurement (FOM) approach [11]. The first rationally supported surveys in this field may be attributed to Binns and Peirce [12,13]. The first systematic approaches useful to factories, however, date back to 1970 with Kawabata and Niwa, who attempted to develop appropriate methods to identify the ideal fabric for clothing applications with respect to subject and season on the basis of its physical mechanical properties [14].

The Australian research agency Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organization (CSIRO) attempted to optimize KESF processes, proposing a faster – but still not rapid – set of tests, called FAST [15].

Time-consuming tests and the high costs of both approaches stimulated further research on the topic, especially on the adoption of the correlation method between subjective sensations generated by fabrics and objective properties obtained through tests on the fabric itself.

This category of study lacks standard procedures, but on the other hand the adoption of successful approaches from different fields, such as foods or cosmetics, are inaccurate and unfavorable to identifying and elaborating sensations provoked by matter in the user.

Hence the intention of developing an easy way to study and predict sensoriality of textiles, especially with respect to the specific senses involved.

3. Objective

This research aims to detect physiological alterations while assessing fabrics and to verify the correlation between sensorial feedback and the physical-mechanical properties of the samples.

As explained in previous studies [6,8], this research intends to identify the connections between emotional loads and corresponding tangible properties – such as softness or smoothness – and the way they can affect human sensing and perceiving. All the design fields share the intention of determining the grammar and syntax of a language to describe the matter and surfaces which interact with our senses, thus exciting profound aspects of our own intellectual, emotional and sensorial reactivity.

The field of textiles manufacturing would benefit enormously from the identification of hand parameters which facilitate the prediction of sensoriality of fabrics in a systematic and sharable way, through values obtained by set processes and a well-defined translational modality. If these hand properties were to be identified they could become a yardstick for judging the “touch and feel” of fabrics. This would enable users and professional figures to communicate easily and understand each other, avoiding doubts and mistakes and thus accelerating communication lapses and optimizing comprehension quality. With this in mind we investigated the sensitivity of both laypeople and experts.

To this purpose we also investigated how the promising field of neurosciences deals with the same topic. For instance, it is possible to understand if a car interior is eye-catching or looks old, or if a website is easy to explore or not, by recording heart-rate and sweat secretion. Similarly, tracking the path of the eyes scanning the environment shows what we first notice on the shelves of a supermarket and can help us understand the way we look at the road while we're driving.

On the basis of the results obtained in our previous studies, recent research has focused on several aspects of the objective forecasting of emotional value in the textiles field, as:

- improving the quality of mechanical tests;
- increasing the number and quality of test subjects;
- applying appropriate testing methodologies developed in the field of neurosciences.

4. Method

Our experiments involved four different groups of homogeneous subjects. Each subject was required to express the sensations and emotions provoked by each of a selection of 8 fabric samples. Samples were perceived in two sensorial modalities, mono-sensorially (sight only) and multi-sensorially (visual and tactile). Each sensory mode was related to a particular aspect of sensoriality of matter, such as texture [16]. Here we aimed to further investigate which factors influence the processing of stimuli to produce a perception of a particular sensorial property, for example which details of the fabric suggested a sensation of softness to the sense of sight.

The properties selected for analysis were softness, smoothness and lightness. Initially, on the basis of both literature [12] and experts' opinion, we selected softness and smoothness as the sensations which most influenced a user's perception of textiles. Considering the results of our previous study [6] we avoided warmth due to problems in consistency of interpretation of this sensation by users. We then decided to add the sensation of lightness in order to further analyze the sensorial panorama.

We then hypothesized the relationship between each sensation and objective properties such as fiber, weaving method and physical and mechanical properties.

The selection of the fabrics group followed a crossed criterion. It included a well-balanced selection which took into consideration both fiber (100% cotton or mixed) and processing (weaving or knitting). Furthermore, all the samples chosen were of a similar color (blue) to reduce transfer phenomena, i.e. the potential influence of this information on tactile perceptions. The final sampling (presented in Table 1 and Figure 1) was sorted as follows: four samples were knitted fabrics and the other four were weave, four were 100% cotton and the others were made of synthetic and artificial fibers (pure or mixed).

Table 1. Final sampling composition.

<i>Code</i>	<i>Fabric name</i>	<i>Yarn</i>	<i>%</i>
1	Canvas	cotton	100
2	Denim	cotton	100
3	Piqué	cotton	100
4	Thick jersey	cotton	100
5	Thin interlock	polyester	100
6	Crêpe	polyester	66
		cotton	33
7	Jersey	viscose	94
		elastam	6
8	Twill weave	polyester	76
		viscose	19
		spandex	6

Figure 1. Final sampling of the 8 selected fabrics.

The research continued with the evaluation of physical mechanical properties. Parameters considered influential in fabric sensitivity were thickness, friction and rigidity. Each parameter was measured using appropriate instruments.

4.1 Objective tests

As previously mentioned, in this phase we attempted to improve the quality and affinity of the mechanical tests adopted in the past.

Rigidity was previously measured using a tensile test [6]. In this step, we investigated procedures which replicate human gestures. For the measurement of softness we selected the Round Hole test [17], an experimental test

which stresses fabric samples in manifold directions at the same time. As in the previous research, the property of smoothness was associated with friction and measured by inclined plane, but carried out this time with coverings imitating human skin.

Finally, lightness was measured with reference to the mechanical parameter of thickness, by optical analysis using a microscope and image analysis software.

The resulting data were analyzed and processed according to manifold perspectives by performing the same test on a specific property in different ways (e.g. on both front and back of the fabric, typically for the friction test) or by extrapolating several data from a single test (e.g. measuring strength and rigidity from the tensile test).

The objective tests performed are summarized in Table 2 together with the resulting mechanical parameters measured and associated to a particular sensorial property.

Table 2. Analyzed sensorial properties associated objective parameters and corresponding tests.

<i>Sensorial Property</i>	<i>Mechanical Parameter</i>	<i>Test</i>
Softness	Rigidity Strength	Round Hole
Smoothness	Friction Coefficient	Inclined Plane
Lightness	Thickness	Micrometer

4.2 Subjective evaluation

This research also aimed to further investigate the correlation between a user's background and sensorial assessment. For this purpose we involved numerous figures sorted and grouped according to aspects such as age, gender and cultural background.

The 8 samples were evaluated by a panel of a total of 78 volunteer subjects, grouped as follows:

- Textile Experts (TE); 4 professional figures who work in the field of textile and clothing;
- Touch Experts (BL), 5 blind people with a highly developed sense of touch to facilitate their daily lives
- Control Group (CG), 69 laypeople unrelated to the study of textiles, sorted by age (46 young people, 12 adults and 11 elderly people) and by gender (37 females and 32 males);
- Foreigners (FO), 14 non-Italian students from five continents.

The involvement of different groups aimed to detect possible tracks of either manifold or univocal approaches to subjective sensoriality. Hence subjects familiar with textile matter were selected in order to check the influence of technical knowledge on the perception experience.

Each subject was invited into an almost soundproof room specifically equipped to provide optimal conditions for sensorial assessment. A panel leader then asked each subject to order the 8 samples in decreasing ranks for each sensorial property (softness, smoothness, lightness). This evaluation was repeated in two perceptual modalities, firstly mono-sensorially (only sight) (Figure 2.a), and then multi-sensorially (Figure 2.b). There was an interval of 50 minutes between each evaluation to avoid transfer phenomena, both positive and negative.

In the first sensorial evaluation phase involving only sight, samples were arranged side by side opposite the subject at a distance of 50 centimetres. Tactile contact was not permitted.

The second, multi-sensorial approach involved both visual and tactile organs through a crossed and simultaneous evaluation of textile sensoriality. The room was dark and only the fabric samples were illuminated.

Figure 2. Users assessing the sampling of fabrics using only sight (a) and multi-sensorially (b).

4.3 Bio-feedback

To avoid time-consuming operations in this phase of earlier general research, a limited group of subjects (14 of the 78 volunteers) underwent bio-feedback recordings.

Biofeedback is an instrument for sensory analysis which arose from the neuroscience in order to relate verbal responses to visible reactions. It allows the evaluation of many parameters in order to identify unconscious mechanisms, such as the heart rate, skin resistance and eye movements. These are the three parameters which were recorded in this research.

Galvanic Skin Resistance (GSR) [18,19] is based on the variation of the electric resistance offered by the skin when the subject is provoked by different emotional stimuli. It is the result of skin humidity brought about by the underlying sweat glands. In fact, the skin acts like a resistor: if we apply two electrodes to the skin, we generally see a weak, constant electrical current, which varies from 10 k Ω to 1 M Ω , between two closed fingers. Starting from a relaxed condition, if a person is stressed skin resistance gradually decreases. External emotional stimuli (a sudden noise, a breath, a phrase, etc...) translate into a drop in electrical resistance in some areas of the body, especially on the palm of the hand.

Heart rate variability gives indications about the variation of the blood flux into the capillaries. This parameter is monitored using photo-optical systems applied to the fingers in order to record the sphygmocystolic waves. It is the key to interpreting the values that are strictly connected to the emotional involvement of the subject.

The *Eye Detection Movement* (EDM) [20] or eye-tracking is a method which can register where a user is looking through the dilation and contraction of the pupils, thus mapping the scan-path of the eyes during an observation. Deductions can be made about what is watched, how information obtained from a picture is processed and which strategies are used for exploration. Furthermore, it allows the identification of what the user excludes from his focus. The eye-tracker is not an invasive device and it is used in many fields: psychology, cognitive linguistics and in product design in order to evaluate the analysis of pictures (advertisements, shop windows, Internet websites, books,...) and to do usability tests (especially households goods).

The extracted data were:

- the average heart rate registered during the tasks of exploration of softness and smoothness (Figure 3.a);
- the average skin resistance registered during the same tasks (Figure 3.a);
- the movements of the eyes during the same tasks and the whole scene that was scanned (Figure 3.b).

Figure 3. User with sensors for heart rate and average skin resistance (a) and eye tracker (b).

5. Results

5.1 Data from sensory analysis

Data resulting from sensory analysis were studied firstly to identify potential shared opinions and emotions while subjects associated hand attributes to textiles.

The extent to which the rankings were shared was assessed using a statistical parameter, Kendall's coefficient W , where the value 0 means that there is no agreement and 1 means total concordance within the group. It takes into account both the number of gaps among the rankings and the extent of any discrepancies.

The resulting concordance values are fully acceptable in psychology research, ranging from a minimum of $W=0.71$ for lightness and reaching their maximum for smoothness ($W=0.82$) and softness ($W=0.87$).

The sharing of rankings occurred not only within a group, but also between groups. For example, the results for the Italian group were similar to the foreign group, which suggests that the former attributes are equally recognized across the different cultures which participated in our research.

We cross-checked the data by analyzing the adjectives used to identify the scales. These adjectives used were synonymous and related to a few well-defined semantic fields, i.e. a full textile was perceived by the majority as heavy and dense, while a rigid textile was considered unbending and strong by the most of the group.

We also expected to discover what guided or diverted the subjects while making the rankings. The questionnaires showed that nearly half of them claimed to have been influenced by the color and the lightness of the samples. They also claimed to have drawn on their previous experience of garments and fabrics and on the rules of fashion, which were more influential for young people rather than older adults.

Finally, a curious result emerged: the favorite sample did not occupy high positions in rankings for softness, smoothness or lightness as might be expected. It was at times placed at the bottom or in the middle of the sensorial rankings. Future studies could further investigate these findings.

5.2 Data from bio-feedback

Bio-feedback data supported our deductions about the difficulties unconsciously perceived by volunteers during each task, i.e. understanding the different sensations (Figure 4).

Considering the short duration of each task, it was necessary to take into account the variation in skin resistance, which is sensitive to short-term physiological variations. In fact, unlike heart rate (HR) variability Galvanic Skin Resistance (GSR) varied as soon as the stimulus began and it changed faster.

The variation was calculated as a percentage of the initial relaxed mood and an average between all the variations during the task. Two tracings were recorded for each test. Not every tracing for GSR and HR from the 14 subjects could be read, however, since some tracings had very tight curves. This means the curves were barely flat and did not appear to change much as time passed. This phenomenon depended on the physiology of the subjects, most of whom were women.

Figure 4. Variation of GSR (on the left) and HR (on the right) as a percentage from the initial relaxed mood and an average among all the variations during the specific task.

The comparison of diagrams of GSR variations permitted the ranking of tasks in increasing order according to level of difficulty:

- smoothness at only sight (average GSR variation: +1%);
- smoothness multi-sensorially (average GSR variation: -7%);
- softness at only sight (average GSR variation: -14%);
- softness multi-sensorially (average GSR variation: -21%).

The average percentage variations of HR were considered only minimally, since the variation was very small (from +2% to +8%). As previously mentioned, this feedback is caused by the slow adaptation of the heart frequency.

Two important results emerge from the comparison of the two scanpath-types. First of all, it is easier to rely on clues originating only from the sense of sight rather than mediate information which comes from two different sensory modes at the same time (touch and sight). Secondly, the creation of the softness ranking appeared to be a more difficult task than creating the smoothness ranking.

Figure 5. Typical scan-path of subjects' visual explorations for: a) softness and b) smoothness sensations, detected by EDM. The percentages indicate the average of time ratio (on the whole time spent) that the subjects used to analyze the corresponding point/edge/area.

This datum is confirmed by the manner in which subjects explored the samples during the sight only test.

The assessment of softness usually required the observer to compare many large areas, to consider the length of the ridges, to estimate the difference in height between ridges and valleys and to evaluate the density of drapes (Figure 5.a).

Ridges were considered according to height and length while the deepest and shallowest valleys were skimmed: the higher the ridges, the more rigid the fabric. Some people observed all of the plies one by one, noticing that some fabrics contain more or less of them. If plies had sharp corners the textile was considered rigid while smooth corners suggested softness. The comparison was often made by observing adjacent samples from left to right. Observations were faster when examining well known textiles (i.e. denim and canvas) and when looking at textiles at extremes of the rankings.

All operations for softness assessment usually took a mean interval of 15 seconds. On the other hand, 10 seconds generally allowed the observer to assess the smoothness of the same sample, because a few small clearly visible areas were sufficient to assess the micro texture of the fabric (Figure 5.b).

In fact, all subjects used the same technique to find cues related to smoothness, focusing their eyes to examine the interweaving of the threads in the textile.

Another important datum about the duration of observation is the fact that in two thirds of cases the multi-sensory approach required more time than the sight only test, even though the materials had already been seen during the session of observation only.

If we assume the period of time necessary to carry out the task as a qualitative scale of measurement to highlight the difficulty in creating a sensorial ranking, we notice a correspondence of such intervals with the difficulty level revealed by the skin-resistance test.

Since a head-mounted eye tracker was used, software could not automatically process quantitative data from the observations. The only way to extract data was watching each video frame by frame or in slow motion afterwards. Unfortunately 15% of videos were useless due to instability or the absence of the red target.

6. Elaboration of results

In the final step, interesting findings were extrapolated from the paired analysis of the results from the three methods described above.

In order to find a potential correlation between the perceived rankings and the measured rankings, the first were used as a touchstone and compared to the mechanical rankings which classified the eight samples according to increasing or decreasing values from the physical mechanical tests.

The concordance was measured using a mathematical index, Spearman's coefficient "k", where the value -1 means that the two scales are reversed, while the value +1 means that they are perfectly concordant. The value 0 indicates the absence of any correlation (neither direct nor inverse).

The correlation between the measured and the perceived scales generated values ranging from $k = 0.93$ for the concordance perceived lightness / measured lightness, and $k = 0.98$ for the concordance perceived smoothness / measured smoothness. The above values – which very nearly coincide with the maximum goal – indicate an almost complete concordance between the mechanical results and sensorial rankings, thus implying an excellent predictability of the sensations investigated using the scientific methods adopted.

Interpreting and summarizing the results, we can affirm that:

- softness sensations can be efficiently predicted by the means of the Round Hole test;
- smoothness sensations can be predicted by a low friction coefficient obtained from the inclined plane test arranged with a weight covered with synthetic leather that slips on a plane covered by the tested sample;
- lightness sensations increase as the thickness value decreases.

7. Conclusions

The research group aimed to verify and further investigate the results of previous research on the predictability of sensorial and emotional properties of textiles. Our purpose was to obtain precious information which can be used by designers and manufacturers when seeking to design and create new textile products with a preferred sensorial profile.

First we investigated and identified the selected hand qualities shared by a panel arranged in groups including professional figures, laypeople, foreign people and blind people.

The predictability of the most influential sensorial properties was studied and demonstrated using common scientific methods and tests, adapted or revised to meet our purposes.

Softness has been confirmed as a highly predictable sensorial property thanks to the experimental multi-axial mechanical tester, faster than common tensile tester.

Predictability of smoothness greatly increased to almost maximum level following the placement of a substratum, which imitated human skin qualities over the testing plane.

Lightness was investigated and correlated to the measurement of thickness with a high level of reliability.

The recordings of the biological feedback offer interesting information in addition to the sensory analysis because they permit the exploration of the semi-conscious and the unconscious responses we experience while exploring a material. In particular, we can understand how difficult it is to perceive certain sensations and where we try to find visual clues to define hand.

The triple analysis method is thus useful in predicting the expressive proprieties of textiles. This method could also be applied to limitless different categories of materials in situations in which we would like to know not only mechanical properties or durability, but also the manner in which materials communicate with their users.

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